

Subject:

Political Science

Title:

**The Other Face of Social Security:
A Special Reference to Elderly People**

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Abstract:

The problem of the elderly people has become one of the major problems in the Indian society. In 21st century modernization and western influence brought many changes in family system of both urban as well as rural life. The traditional values and norms of families lost its glaze. Elderly person are mostly victimized of this changing structure of Indian family system. The problems of elderly are multi-dimensional although both the central government and states governments are formulating various welfare schemes for old people these are inadequate and not satisfactory. This research article study about the various issues of elderly people in India.

Keywords:

Elderly people, modernization, welfare schemes, victimize

LYCEUM INDIAJournal of **Social Sciences****Introduction:**

“Youth Can Walk Faster, But The Elder Knows the Road”

- African proverb

The above quote of African proverb depicts the significance of elderly persons for the betterment of society. Elderly, growing and aging is just an unavoidable natural process that every individual experiences. Today more than 727 million people are aged about 65 years or above it across world (world population aging report 2020). It is a systematic process that when individual grows in age, there is a progressive decline in their physical and cognitive abilities. This makes older peoples frail and they lose more and more control over their own daily activities and their dependence on others increases. This losing ability and agility on the one hand and need for others support on the other makes the people surrounding them, isolate them and exploit them. Gradually they became unable to get their basic rights like adequate nutrition, housing, health care and mostly economic security.

Status of elderly people in India

Traditionally, our Indian society has largely been an agrarian economy based society. The value based family system of Indian society was rich in ideological tradition and culturally sound because of joint family system. The joint family system prevailed in these societies, where the older persons in the family control over family's financial transactions, social interactions and day to day affairs. They were highly respected in the family apart from this care and respect for elders in the family was part of the social value system in Indian culture and tradition. The decision making power was held by the family 's eldest, who was often referred to as the head of the family. Gradually within the existing of globalization and modern life, joint family system collapsed. The agrarian based economy moving towards technology and non -agro economy. The rural lifestyles affected by the urban lifestyles as a results most of the rural youths they shifted towards urban societies because of education, better job opportunity, good earning sources and better lifestyles. Gradually the big collective families segregated in to small nucleus families. This transformation makes many difficulties for the old peoples in India. They feel vulnerable, lonely and abandoned.

Issues of elderly rights

In our society the elderly persons are the vulnerable sections those who are voiceless for their rights .in our day to day life they face many challenges because of their aging and physical incapability. Some persons are abandoned from their houses by their children and other relatives.

1. Loneliness and social insecurity-

Loneliness and social insecurity is a prime issue amongst elderly people in India. Different physiological changes in the body leading to ill health such as arthritis, paralysis or old age weakness, senior citizens mostly remain indoors and they gradually get isolated from the outer social life, family and their friend circle. Within the family also they face isolation due to the busy schedule of present generation and digital life of family members. The senior citizens are gradually unwanted and getting marginalized in family system. Generally, children are now busy and some of them have money to take care of their parents but they may not have enough time for giving proper attention.

2. Physical insecurity

In the 21st century the competitive life styles of the people result in the improper family relationship and isolated life styles. Many senior citizens when they have to depend upon their children they found themselves in Hospitals, Temples, Mathas and Gurudwaras where no one cares what happens to them. The elderly people face different physical barriers and challenges in day to day life. Such as

- (A) Physical abuse and neglect of senior citizens
- (B) Crime against senior citizens
- (C) Barriers in accessing services
- (D) Lack of proper elder- friendly transportation services
- (E) Digital barriers etc.

3. Financial in security

Financial insecurity is a worst cause of violation of elderly rights. If the elderly has no money or property with them and are economically dependent on their children most of the cases they are abused and insulted for their dependence and they unable to purchase a cup of tea, a packet of biscuit or even medicine. Basically in developing country like India people have unplanned about their old age financial security and their children are also not so serious about this. And finally the elderly life became very painful.

4. Health care issues –

In India the elderly people face the different type of health issues due to age or other causes. Generally hearing impairment is common affecting almost 25% adults in between the age group of 65-74 and 50% adults of 75 age and older. Vision difficulties are common amongst the old people. More than one third of people over the age group of 65 are affected by falls every year. The bladder and urinary tract becomes less elastic, which can make it difficult to empty bladder completely. Apart from this tooth decay, low bone density and sleeping problems are the major health problems amongst the elderly people. The present generation is not so serious about the problems of elders in their family.

Welfare schemes for elderly persons

(1) Rastriya vayoshri yojana(RVY)-

This scheme is only available to those senior citizens who are in below poverty line that is BPL card holder. Senior citizens suffering from low vision, hearing impairment, loss of teeth and loco motor disability will be provided assisted living devices. Apart from this walking sticks, elbow crutches, hearing aids that are provided under this scheme. This scheme was launched in 2017 by the ministry of social justice and empowerment of government of India.

(2) Indira Gandhi national old age pension scheme-

This scheme was introduced in 2007 by the ministry of rural development of government of India and popularly known as national old age pension scheme (NOAPS). This scheme provides social assistance benefits to senior citizens, widows and those with disabilities. Under this scheme beneficiary will receive a monthly pension.

(3) National Programme for the Health Care of Elderly(NPHCE)

The ministry of health and family welfare had launched the national programme for the health care of elderly (NPHCE) during 2010-11 to address various health related problems of elderly people. The following facilities are being provided under the programme.

- ❖ Geriatric OPD and 10 bedded geriatric ward at district hospitals.
- ❖ Bi-weekly geriatric clinic at community health centres (CHC).
- ❖ Weekly geriatric clinic at primary health centre (PHC).

(4) Madhubabu Pension Yojana (MBPY)-

This scheme is very popular and beneficial scheme under the department of social security and empowerment of persons with disabilities for the disabled, old age persons in Odisha. The Madhubabu Pensions Yojana was launched by former chief minister of Odisha on 01-01-2008 by merging the two pension schemes namely revised old age pension rules 1989 and disabilities pension rules 1985.

Discussion

In today's globalized world, the problems of elderly are different and complex. In urban lifestyles craze for competition and materialistic attitudes of children brought loneliness for elderly. In city life many elderly are remain either alone or with their spouse. They are actually emotionally alone and physically unfit. Although they have sound financial condition but socially and emotionally isolated. generally, this social problem is known as "empty nest". The problems of Elderly people those who are living in rural areas in their case many problems are still unsolved, although the government of central and states formulate varieties of welfare schemes for elderly these are not satisfactory implemented. Many welfare schemes are still unreached for old people. During the time of election manifesto political parties are unwilling to emphasize the needs and requirements of old persons, so elderly problems remain unsolved. In real sense, we cannot develop our state without the development of old people. It is high time to consider the importance of old people for the present generation.

The aging process is of course a biological reality which has its own impact, largely beyond human control. The rights of elderly are equally same important like the rights of women and children in society. Traditionally elder care has been the responsibility of families as well as society members. But in modern societies abuses are taking place more and more in societies and homes instead of providing care. Generally isolated life of elderly and negligence by family members, relatives in societies which pushes them to the dark corners of loneliness.

Recommendations and conclusion

The above discussion makes it clear that the problems of elderly people are very complex and deep rooted. Although both the central and states governments schemes are being implemented for the welfare of old people these are not satisfactory and inadequate also. Once mother Teresa said that –“loneliness and the feeling of being unwanted is the most terrible poverty in the world”. Which hints for the need of psycho-social management strategies for a better old age? Certain strategies should be followed for the proper management of old age. In the first place family members should provide companionship to old people. Secondly emotional support and motivation also essential for the happy and dignified life. Thirdly providing education and information on topic relevant to aging such as health care options, retirements planning etc. are required. Fourthly there should be technological assistance to old people to using computers smart phones, online platforms etc. providing technological assistance and training can help the elderly people to connect with digital world. And finally the financial support is most essential requirement of every elderly person.

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